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THE IMPACT OF FLIPGRID ON IRAQI EFL LEARNERS' MOTIVATION IN LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

Despite the growing integration of digital tools in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) instruction, many Iraqi EFL learners continue to exhibit low motivation in learning English due to teacher-centered approaches, limited opportunities for interaction, and minimal use of technology-enhanced learning platforms. Although studies in other contexts have reported the motivational benefits of video-based discussion tools such as FlipGrid, empirical evidence on its effectiveness in enhancing Iraqi EFL learners' motivation remains scarce. Thus, this study, examines the impact of FlipGrid on Iraqi EFL learners' motivation and their perceptions of its use in learning English. The study adopted a pre- and post-test quasi-experimental research design. An intact class of 60 second-year undergraduate students aged 19 to 21 from a local university in Iraq participated in the study. The treatment, which involved integrating FlipGrid into English language instruction, was conducted over a period of 12 weeks. Data were collected using two questionnaires measuring learners' motivation and perceptions, as well as a semi-structured questionnaire to elicit in-depth responses. The motivation questionnaire was administered before and after the treatment. Quantitative data were analyzed using paired-sample t-tests and descriptive statistics. The findings revealed a statistically significant improvement in learners' motivation after the FlipGrid-based instruction. In addition, the participants expressed positive perceptions of FlipGrid as an engaging and interactive learning tool, although some challenges related to technology use were reported. The study concludes by offering pedagogical implications and recommendations for future research and instructional practice.

KEYWORDS: Flipgrid, EFL Learners, Learning Motivation, Educational Technology, Iraqi Context.

1. INTRODUCTION

English has become a dominant global language for communication, education, technology, and international relations (Aliakbari, 2010). Its role in globalization and technological advancement has led many countries to adopt English as a second or foreign language in order to participate effectively in the global economy, politics, and cross-cultural communication. Consequently, proficiency in English has become an essential requirement for students in non-English-speaking countries, including Iraq. However, despite the substantial amount of time Iraqi learners spend studying English from secondary to tertiary levels, many EFL undergraduates continue to demonstrate low proficiency in English at undergraduate levels. Previous studies have consistently reported that Iraqi university students experience serious difficulties in speaking English fluently, accurately, and confidently (Bueno, Madrid, & McLaren, 2006; Ahmed, 2012). These difficulties are often manifested in learners' reluctance to speak, fear of making oral errors, limited speaking ability, and lack of supportive peer interaction (Keong, Abdalhussein, & Mohammed, 2015). In addition, low motivation has been identified as a critical factor contributing to learners' negative attitudes toward speaking English and, more broadly, toward English language learning (Ahmed et al., 2021).

Scholars have attributed these challenges largely to the instructional methods commonly employed in Iraqi EFL classrooms. Traditional approaches such as the Grammar Translation Method and Audio-Lingual Method, as well as limited implementation of the Communicative Approach which tend to emphasize linguistic forms over meaningful interaction. These mostly restrict opportunities for authentic communication and learner engagement (Khalil, 2018). As a result, students often experience high levels of speaking anxiety and low motivation, which further hinder their oral language development. This situation highlights the urgent need for innovative and learner-centered approaches that can motivate Iraqi EFL learners, reduce speaking anxiety, increase their motivation and improve their speaking proficiency (Al-Abdali & Alzayadi, 2020).

One promising direction in addressing these challenges is the integration of educational technology in language learning. Technology-based approaches such as Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL), Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC), and Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) have been shown to enhance learner motivation, interaction, and

language performance. In particular, task-based approaches supported by technology encourage learners to collaborate, negotiate meaning, and actively use the target language in meaningful contexts (Robinson, 2001; Edge, 1986). In virtual learning environments, such approaches allow students to complete communicative tasks collaboratively through online platforms, thereby extending learning beyond the physical classroom.

FlipGrid is an asynchronous video-based discussion platform that has gained increasing attention in language education. It provides learners with opportunities to practice speaking in a supportive and low-anxiety environment, enabling them to record, review, and share video responses at their own pace. Previous studies have shown that FlipGrid can enhance students' speaking skills, reduce speaking anxiety, and increase engagement and motivation (Razak, Saed, & Alakrash, 2020; Lamb, 2020). It is particularly beneficial for learners who experience fear of making mistakes, shyness, or lack of confidence when speaking in front of others, as well as those who have limited time for in-class speaking practice (Tan, 2019).

Despite the growing global adoption of ICT tools in EFL classrooms, their use in the Iraqi context remains limited. Studies have reported that technology integration in Iraqi English classrooms is constrained by factors such as limited access to technological resources, insufficient training, and negative attitudes among both teachers and students (Ahmed, Puteh-Behak, & Sidek, 2015; Borg, 2016; Ghareb & Mohammed, 2017). Particularly, the use of FlipGrid as a pedagogical tool in Iraqi EFL classrooms has received little scholarly attention. Although a few studies have explored technology-enhanced English learning among Iraqi learners, their focus has been limited. For example, Mussa (2020) investigated Iraqi secondary students' motivation toward e-learning in Malaysia and found positive attitudes toward technology-based learning. Similarly, Khudhair (2021) reported that Iraqi secondary school students had favourable perceptions of using mobile phones for learning English. However, empirical studies examining the use of FlipGrid to enhance Iraqi EFL learners' motivation in learning English at the university level are scarce. Thus, the present study investigates the use of FlipGrid in an Iraqi university EFL classroom to examine its effectiveness in enhancing learners' motivation and to explore their perceptions of the platform in learning English.

1.1. Research Questions

1. What are the effects of FlipGrid on Iraqi EFL learners' motivation in learning English?
2. What are the Iraqi EFL learners' perceptions of using FlipGrid in learning English speaking?

2. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design to investigate Iraqi EFL learners' motivation and perceptions regarding the use of FlipGrid in English language learning.

2.1. Research Site

The study was conducted at a public university in Iraq, a well-established institution known for its diverse academic programs and a large population of students studying English as a Foreign Language (EFL). The selection of this research site was purposeful, as the university provides a representative context for examining the integration of technology-based language learning tools within Iraqi EFL classrooms. The study focused on undergraduate EFL learners enrolled in English language courses, offering an appropriate setting to explore the effectiveness of FlipGrid in enhancing learners' speaking skills and motivation.

2.2. Participants Of the Study

The participants consisted of an intact class of 60 second-year undergraduate students selected from a local university in Iraq. As noted by Creswell (2012), classroom-based research may involve selecting an entire class as the research sample to minimize bias, making random selection or group assignment unnecessary. The participants included both male and female students aged between 19 and 21 years. Specifically, the students were EFL learners at the University of Baghdad. English had been introduced to them formally from the age of seven during their primary education, and all participants spoke Arabic as their first language (L1).

2.3. Instruments For Data Collection

Two questionnaires were employed to collect data on participants' motivation and perceptions regarding the use of FlipGrid in English language learning.

1. Flipgrid Perception Questionnaire

The FlipGrid Perception Questionnaire was adapted from Tuyet and Khang (2020) to examine participants' perceptions and experiences of using the FlipGrid platform for online learning practice. The questionnaire was designed to capture students' attitudes toward the platform's usefulness, ease of

use, and perceived impact on their English-speaking skills. The items covered key aspects such as learner engagement, collaboration, feedback, and improvement in speaking performance. The interactive features of FlipGrid, particularly its asynchronous video-recording function, were expected to positively influence learners' perceptions of English learning practice.

2. Motivation Questionnaire

The second instrument was a Speaking Motivation Questionnaire adapted from Baresh (2018), which was originally developed based on Wang's (2008) motivational framework. This questionnaire aimed to assess participants' motivation toward speaking English before and after the FlipGrid intervention.

It measured both intrinsic and extrinsic motivational components, including:

- Motivation for Knowledge: The desire to learn and acquire new language skills.
- Motivation to Accomplish: The drive to complete tasks and improve performance.
- External Utility Regulation: Motivation influenced by external rewards or utility, such as academic success or career advancement.
- Internal Fulfillment Regulation: Motivation stemming from personal satisfaction and internal rewards.
- English Achievement: Motivation linked to success in learning English as a measure of accomplishment.

All items were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). The questionnaires have been widely used and validated in previous language learning studies, thereby ensuring their reliability and credibility (see Appendix for details).

2.4. Data Collection

Data were collected over a 12-week period, corresponding to nearly one academic semester. This duration was considered sufficient to allow meaningful engagement with the FlipGrid platform and to observe changes in learners' motivation and speaking-related experiences. At the outset of the study, formal permission was obtained from the university, and informed consent was secured from all participants. The consent forms clearly explained the purpose, procedures, and ethical considerations of the study, emphasizing voluntary participation, confidentiality, and anonymity.

To establish baseline motivation levels, the motivation questionnaire was administered as a pre-

test before the introduction of FlipGrid. Following this, participants took part in a 12-week FlipGrid-based speaking intervention. FlipGrid, an asynchronous video discussion platform, enabled students to record and share video responses to speaking prompts provided by the researcher. The platform is compatible with multiple devices, including mobile phones and computers (Lowenthal & Moore, 2020). The researcher served as the grid administrator and designed speaking tasks aligned with the Iraqi communicative English textbook. Topics included *My Hometown*, *My Favorite Food*, and *My Favorite Movie*. Visual and multimedia prompts such as images, videos, and external links were incorporated to stimulate discussion (Petersen, Townsend, & Onaka, 2020). Students accessed the platform through a shared URL and submitted their video responses asynchronously.

Participants attended two face-to-face English classes per week, during which they practiced conversational activities such as greetings, pair work, and structured speaking tasks. For additional practice, students recorded and submitted FlipGrid videos as homework, applying vocabulary and structures learned in class. At the end of the intervention, the motivation questionnaire was re-administered as a post-test to assess changes in learners' motivation. Subsequently, the FlipGrid Perception Questionnaire was administered to collect participants' views on the platform's effectiveness, challenges, and overall learning experience.

2.5. Data Analysis

To address the first research question, *what are the effects of FlipGrid on Iraqi EFL learners' motivation in learning English?* a paired-sample *t*-test was conducted to compare participants' pre- and post-test motivation scores. For the second research question, *what are Iraqi EFL learners' perceptions of using FlipGrid in learning English speaking?* descriptive statistical analyses were employed. Means, frequencies, and standard deviations were calculated to summarize participants' responses to the perception questionnaire.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Effects Of Flipgrid on Iraqi EFL Learners' Motivation in Learning English

To determine the effects of FlipGrid on Iraqi EFL learners' motivation to learn English speaking, descriptive and inferential statistical analyses were conducted using data obtained from the pre- and post-treatment motivation questionnaires. The

questionnaire measured multiple dimensions of motivation which include enjoyment of speaking, persistence in overcoming difficulties, confidence, task engagement, goal orientation, and both intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors.

The descriptive results indicated an overall increase in the post-treatment mean scores across all questionnaire items which suggest a positive shift in learners' motivation following the FlipGrid intervention. To determine whether these changes were statistically significant, a paired-sample *t*-test was performed to compare the pre- and post-treatment mean scores. The results revealed a highly significant improvement in learners' motivation after the intervention ($t = -27.66, p = .000$) which confirm that FlipGrid had a substantial positive impact on participants' motivation to engage in English learning activities.

Table 1 presents the pre- and post-treatment mean scores and standard deviations for each motivation item. Across all items, post-treatment means (M2) were considerably higher than pre-treatment means (M1) which indicate improvements in enjoyment, confidence, persistence, and goal-oriented motivation. For instance, learners' enjoyment of speaking English (Item 1) increased markedly from M1 = 2.18 to M2 = 4.20, suggesting that FlipGrid created a more engaging and enjoyable speaking environment. Similarly, persistence in overcoming speaking difficulties (Item 2) rose from M1 = 2.70 to M2 = 4.30, reflecting greater resilience and willingness to practice despite challenges. These improvements can be attributed to FlipGrid's asynchronous design, which allows learners to rehearse, revise, and re-record their responses without the immediate pressure of live performance.

One of the most outstanding gains was observed in learners' speaking confidence (Item 4), which increased from M1 = 2.90 to M2 = 4.70. This finding indicates that FlipGrid's low-anxiety environment supported learners' self-confidence by reducing fear of negative evaluation. The opportunity to review and refine recordings before submission likely contributed to this increased confidence.

Learners also demonstrated improved self-regulation and task management. The item related to planning and completing speaking assignments (Item 5) increased from M1 = 2.50 to M2 = 4.60, suggesting that structured FlipGrid tasks encouraged more deliberate and organized speaking practice. Furthermore, learners became more willing to engage in challenging speaking tasks (Item 7), with mean scores increasing from M1 = 2.80 to M2 = 4.40, highlighting increased intrinsic motivation and task

engagement.

Both intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors showed significant gains. For example, motivation related to personal development (Item 6) increased from $M1 = 2.58$ to $M2 = 4.40$, while recognition of English as an important communication tool (Item

18) rose from $M1 = 2.70$ to $M2 = 4.52$. The largest improvement was observed in Item 14 ("I seldom finished English speaking homework"), which increased from $M1 = 2.88$ to $M2 = 4.80$, indicating a substantial shift toward active task completion and engagement.

Table 1: Participants' Motivation for Speaking English.

S/N	Items	M1	SD1	M2	SD2
1	I like speaking English.	2.1833	1.34658	4.2000	.60506
2	I will persist when facing difficulties in speaking English.	2.7000	1.01347	4.3000	.64572
3	I do all my oral English exercises actively.	3.2833	1.04300	4.3000	.64572
4	I feel more confident in speaking English compared with my classmates.	2.9000	1.14537	4.7000	.46212
5	I work on my English-speaking assignments according to a planned schedule.	2.5000	.92973	4.6000	.49403
6	I speak English diligently for potential development in the future.	2.5833	.92593	4.4000	.66892
7	I like challenging and difficult tasks in English speaking.	2.8000	.87914	4.4000	.66892
8	I consider the English oral examination as an evaluation of what I have learned about English.	2.6000	.80675	4.5000	.67648
9	I like imitating English spoken in movies.	2.7167	1.12131	4.6000	.49403
10	I am excited when I have accomplished a difficult task in English speaking.	2.6333	1.04097	4.4000	.49403
11	I try to speak English hard for the praise of the teacher.	2.3167	1.38383	4.1000	.54306
12	I seldom speak English outside of English class.	2.3000	.78762	4.3000	.64572
13	I am learning to speak English only to pass the examination at the University	2.8333	.76284	4.3167	.62414
14	I seldom finished English speaking homework.	2.8833	1.23634	4.8000	.40338
15	It is very challenging to communicate with foreign speakers.	2.2000	.87914	4.4000	.66892
16	The English achievement is a crucial factor in getting the scholarship, so I speak English diligently.	2.4000	.80675	4.3167	.77002
17	I speak English diligently merely to graduate from university.	2.5000	.81303	4.4333	.64746
18	English is a very important tool for communication so I speak it diligently.	2.7000	.90760	4.5167	.65073
19	In order to get an ideal job in the future, I learn to speak English diligently.	2.7000	1.10928	4.3000	.78762
20	English speaking takes great advantage on the future work.	2.5000	.92973	4.2000	.75465

M1=pre-test mean; SD1= pre-test standard deviation

M2=post-test mean; SD1= post-test standard deviation

The paired-sample t-test results (Table 2) further confirmed these findings which show a significant mean difference of 35.85 between pre- and post-treatment motivation scores ($p < .05$). This

demonstrates that FlipGrid not only enhanced learners' enjoyment of speaking English but also strengthened their academic and career-related motivation.

Table 2: Paired-Sample T-Test for the Pre- and Post-Treatment Motivation Scores (N=60).

Components	Pre-tr. Mean	Post-tr. Mean	Mean Diff.	SD	t value	Sig. (2 tailed)
Students' Motivation	52.233	88.0833	35.85	1.295	-27.66	.000

4. DISCUSSION

The findings of this study demonstrate that integrating FlipGrid into EFL instruction significantly enhanced Iraqi EFL learners' motivation and speaking performance. The substantial post-treatment gains in motivation across confidence, persistence, enjoyment, and goal orientation indicate that FlipGrid effectively addressed key affective barriers commonly faced by Iraqi EFL learners, such as speaking anxiety and fear of making mistakes.

In the Iraqi EFL context, where instruction is often teacher-centred and opportunities for authentic speaking practice are limited, FlipGrid represents a meaningful pedagogical innovation. Its

asynchronous, video-based format provides learners with repeated opportunities for practice, reflection, and self-correction, supporting autonomous learning in environments where individualized feedback is often scarce. The observed improvements in fluency, pronunciation, vocabulary, accuracy, and comprehension further demonstrate how technology-enhanced speaking practice can compensate for constraints such as large class sizes and limited classroom interaction.

From a theoretical perspective, the findings align with Constructivist Theory (Vygotsky, 1978), which emphasizes learning through social interaction and reflective practice. FlipGrid facilitated peer

interaction, feedback, and self-reflection, enabling learners to construct knowledge collaboratively while progressing at their own pace. The results also support the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989), as learners' increased motivation and confidence reflect positive perceptions of FlipGrid's usefulness and ease of use. Additionally, the study aligns with Task-Based Learning (TBL) principles (Ellis, 2003), as learners engaged in meaningful, real-world speaking tasks that emphasized communication over form-focused instruction.

The findings corroborate previous studies reporting positive effects of FlipGrid on speaking skills, motivation, and learner autonomy (Diflippantonio-Pen, 2020; Tuyet & Khang, 2020; Miskam & Saidalvi, 2019; Hung, 2021). Similar to these studies, the present research confirms that repeated practice, peer feedback, and contextualized tasks contribute to improved speaking performance and sustained motivation. Although some technical challenges related to internet connectivity were reported, these did not outweigh the pedagogical benefits of the platform.

Overall, the results indicate that FlipGrid provides a supportive, engaging, and learner-centered environment that enhances motivation and promotes consistent speaking practice. Its integration into Iraqi EFL classrooms offers a practical and scalable solution for improving speaking instruction, fostering learner autonomy, and bridging the gap between traditional teaching methods and technology-enhanced learning.

4.1. Participants Perceptions of the Use of Flipgrid

The results of the descriptive statistical analysis indicate that participants held highly positive perceptions of the use of Flipgrid in English language classrooms. Overall, the majority of participants agreed with all the questionnaire items, demonstrating strong acceptance of Flipgrid as an effective tool for enhancing their English-speaking skills. Among the questionnaire items, Item 3 recorded the highest mean score ($M = 4.0465$, $SD = .53623$) which indicate that most participants believed that learning English speaking would be more effective with the use of Flipgrid. This finding suggests that students perceive the platform's unique

features such as asynchronous video recording, opportunities for repeated practice, and the provision of feedback as beneficial for improving their speaking abilities. Flipgrid's capacity to offer a flexible, interactive, and personalized learning environment likely contributed to this perception, as it allows students to practice speaking without the time pressure or anxiety commonly associated with live classroom speaking activities.

Item 1, which examined Flipgrid's role in enhancing cooperation and communication among classmates, also yielded a high mean score ($M = 4.0185$, $SD = .33359$). This result further supports the view that Flipgrid fosters collaborative learning. Participants reported that practicing English speaking through Flipgrid increased their interaction with peers which is likely due to the platform's emphasis on peer engagement and video-based feedback. The ability to watch and respond to classmates' recordings promotes a sense of community and encourages students to learn from one another's strengths and mistakes.

Similarly, participants expressed a strong desire for Flipgrid to be used more frequently in speaking classrooms. This is reflected in Item 16 ($M = 4.0185$, $SD = .33359$) where participants indicated that the use of Flipgrid makes learning more enjoyable and engaging. The interactive and multimedia-based nature of the platform contrasts with traditional lecture-based approaches commonly used in Iraqi classrooms, which makes speaking practice more dynamic and enjoyable. These positive perceptions of enjoyment and motivation highlight Flipgrid's potential to increase classroom participation and reduce boredom in language learning.

The findings also emphasise the role of Flipgrid in enhancing learner autonomy. Item 2, which measured the extent to which Flipgrid promotes independent speaking practice, recorded a mean score of $M = 3.9953$ ($SD = .35517$). This suggests that many participants felt empowered to take control of their own learning when using Flipgrid. The asynchronous format of the platform enables students to record, review, and refine their responses at their own pace. This aligns closely with principles of self-regulated learning. Such autonomy encourages reflection and self-assessment, both of which are critical for developing fluency and accuracy in spoken language.

Table 3: Participants' Perceptions of the Use of Flipgrid.

S/N	Items	M	SD
1	I believe that practising English speaking using Flipgrid has helped increase my cooperation and communication with my classmates.	4.0185	.33359
2	I believe that Flipgrid makes me autonomous in English-speaking practices.	3.9953	.35517

3	I believe that learning English speaking will be effective with the use of Flipgrid.	4.0465	.53623
4	I am less frightened about making mistakes when learning English-speaking through the use of Flipgrid.	3.8194	.63962
5	I consider Flipgrid a great English learning tool.	3.8940	.53818
6	I feel comfortable practising speaking English through the use of Flipgrid.	3.9533	.60333
7	I believe that Flipgrid has helped me reduce my nervousness in learning English speaking.	3.8785	.66728
8	I believe that the use of Flipgrid has helped me become self-confident in my speaking performance.	3.9065	.59785
9	I am responsible for my English learning when using Flipgrid.	3.9907	.57862
10	I believe that Flipgrid has helped me speak English more fluently.	3.9628	.66171
11	I believe that Flipgrid has helped me better improve my pronunciation.	3.8889	.58403
12	I believe that practising English speaking using Flipgrid has helped me better communicate with my teachers.	3.9579	.59977
13	I believe that practising English speaking using Flipgrid has helped me recognize mistakes.	3.9299	.56481
14	Learning using Flipgrid encouraged me to practice speaking in English.	3.9539	.71860
15	I would like to study English speaking without the use of Flipgrid.	3.8194	.63962
16	I hope Flipgrid is used more frequently to make English-speaking learning more fun.	4.0185	.33359
17	I hope Flipgrid will enable me to study English speaking more efficiently.	3.8940	.53818
18	I think I will continue using Flipgrid for English-speaking learning in the future.	3.9953	.35517

The positive perceptions expressed by the participants provide strong evidence that Flipgrid is perceived as a valuable tool for enhancing English-speaking skills in an EFL context. The ability of the platform to reduce speaking anxiety, enhance collaboration, and promote learner autonomy addresses key challenges faced by Iraqi students learning English. In traditional classrooms, students often have limited opportunities for real-world speaking practice, and large class sizes may hinder individualized feedback. Flipgrid offers a student-centered, interactive alternative which allows learners to practice speaking in a supportive environment where they feel less pressure and more control over their learning experience.

Furthermore, the strong emphasis on collaboration and communication suggests that integrating Flipgrid into speaking activities helps build a sense of community among students. Language learning is inherently social, and platforms that facilitate peer interaction contribute to the development of communicative competence. This aligns with constructivist theories of learning, which posit that knowledge is constructed through social interaction and collaboration.

The result of the descriptive statistical analysis is supported by the participants' responses to the semi-structured interviews. The responses gained from the semi-structured interviews also revealed the participants' positive perceptions of the use of Flipgrid in the learning English. According to them, the use of FlipGrid helps them in numerous ways such as overcoming speaking anxiety, and increasing their fluency, and vocabulary among other things. Although the participants had some challenges in using Flipgrid, they believe its benefits outweigh the problems. Therefore, they hope to use it in all their

courses. The following subsections present the themes obtained from the interview responses.

Overcoming Speaking Anxiety by Using Flipgrid

In the interviews, participants consistently expressed a shared struggle with speaking anxiety in traditional English classrooms. The introduction of Flipgrid was seen as a transformative tool, providing a supportive environment for the participants to practice speaking without the fear of immediate judgment. This theme reflects the positive impact of Flipgrid in building participants' confidence and alleviating anxiety associated with speaking in a foreign language. This theme centres around how the use of Flipgrid contributes to the participants' ability to overcome anxiety associated with speaking in English classrooms. Flipgrid provides a platform for the participants to record themselves, promoting a low-pressure environment for practice and self-assessment. The participants also reported that using Flipgrid in English speaking Classroom helped them to overcome speaking anxiety. For instance, a participant explained that using Flipgrid helped him overcome his anxiety about speaking in English. He added that he always felt nervous during in-class discussions, but with Flipgrid, he could practice until he felt confident in himself. Most importantly, Flipgrid allowed him to speak in English without feeling like everyone was watching him in real time.

Using Flipgrid helped me get over my fear of speaking in English. I always felt nervous during in-class discussions, but with Flipgrid, I could practice until I felt confident. It's like having a conversation without feeling like everyone's watching you in real time. (Participant 12)

Another participant added that he did not only

enjoy the Flipgrid platform but also found it liberating, because he could redo his video until he got it just right. It took away the pressure, and he started enjoying expressing himself in English without that constant worry about making mistakes.

I found it liberating, you know. I could redo my video until I got it just right. It took away the pressure, and I started enjoying expressing myself in English without that constant worry about making mistakes. (Participant 15)

Another participant also explained that using Flipgrid made him more comfortable speaking in English. This is because he could practice without the pressure of a live audience. As the result, his speaking anxiety reduced significantly.

Using Flipgrid made me more comfortable speaking in English. I could practice without the pressure of a live audience, which reduced my anxiety.

(Participant 21)

For another participant, before the use of Flipgrid in their classroom, he was hesitant to speak in class. However, after using the Flipgrid platform, she felt more confident because she could record and review her speech before sharing it with other students.

Before Flipgrid, I was hesitant to speak in class. Now, I feel more confident because I can record and review my speech before sharing it with others.

(Participant 21)

This theme highlights the transformative potential of Flipgrid in addressing speaking anxiety among Iraqi learners of English as a foreign language. It also shows the potential of the platform in creating a more positive and encouraging atmosphere for language practice.

Improving Fluency Through Using Flipgrid in English Speaking Classroom

Fluency in spoken English is a multifaceted skill involving not just correct pronunciation but also a smooth and natural flow of speech. This theme emerged from the interview responses and explains how Flipgrid helped in the enhancement of the participants' fluency in spoken English. The platform allows for repeated recording and playback, enabling participants to refine their pronunciation, intonation, and overall speech flow.

The participants recognized Flipgrid as a personal fluency coach, enabling them to refine various aspects of their spoken language skills. The process of recording, reviewing, and adjusting contributed significantly to the enhancement of fluency. The participants also reported that using Flipgrid in English speaking classrooms helped them to increase fluency. For example, a participant explained that he

observed improvement in his fluency because he could go over his recordings and see where he made mistakes and corrected them before submitting the final one. He considered that as having a language tutor giving you feedback, but you are the one in control, deciding where to improve.

I noticed an improvement in my fluency because I could go over my recordings and see where I hesitated. It's like having a language tutor giving you feedback, but you're the one in control, deciding where to improve.s (Participant 7)

Another participant remarked that Flipgrid became his go-to tool for improving fluency. He could repeat recordings until he felt my speech flowed naturally. It was not just about speaking; it was about getting the rhythm and pace right."

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For another participant, Flipgrid is considered as her speaking fluency trainer. She could record, listen, and adjust until she spoke smoothly. She sees it as a step-by-step process to fluency.

Flipgrid became my personal fluency trainer. I could record, listen, and adjust until I spoke smoothly. It's a step-by-step process to fluency.

Another participant also explained that the more she used Flipgrid, the more fluent she became. This enabled her to not just increase their speaking speed but also help her to get the rhythm and flow of English right.

The more I used Flipgrid, the more fluent I became.

It's not just about speaking; it's about getting the rhythm and flow of English right.

The platform provided a structured yet flexible approach to fluency development, allowing students to focus on specific aspects of their speech, be it pronunciation, intonation, or overall coherence. The findings suggested that through consistent use of Flipgrid, participants perceived a significant improvement in their fluency after using the platform. They consider the platform as an essential component of their language learning process.

Increasing Vocabulary Through Using Flipgrid in English Speaking Classroom

Vocabulary enrichment emerged as a significant outcome of Flipgrid usage. This theme explains how engaging with the platform prompted the participants to explore a more diverse range of words and expressions. The dynamic topics presented on Flipgrid acted as catalysts for vocabulary expansion, encouraging students to seek out and incorporate

new and nuanced language into their spoken English. The participants also reported that using Flipgrid in English speaking Classroom helped them to increase the range of their vocabulary. For instance, a participant explains that getting feedback from his classmates greatly helped him to increase the number of his vocabulary. He explained that he learned new words and phrases from them. It is like they were all teaching each other. It made the whole language-learning thing more fun

Getting feedback from classmates was great. I learned new words and phrases from them. It's like we were all teaching each other. It made the whole language-learning thing more fun. (Participant 5)

Another participant also shared his experiences that Flipgrid pushed him to think beyond the basic words I was comfortable with. Discussing various topics made me search for the right words to express myself more precisely. It's like a vocabulary expansion tool for me."

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A participant explained that the topic given for the Flipgrid videos pushed him to think creatively and use new words. As a result, his vocabulary expanded because he wanted to express himself more precisely.

Flipgrid topics pushed me to think creatively and use new words. My vocabulary expanded because I wanted to express myself more precisely.

For another participant, the topics on Flipgrid encouraged him to search for and use diverse words to enable him to express his points clearly. He considered Flipgrid as a vocabulary expansion tool.

The topics on Flipgrid encouraged me to search for and use diverse words. It's like a vocabulary expansion tool for me.

The theme suggests Flipgrid was found to be a tool for vocabulary expansion among the participants. The platform encouraged participants to explore and incorporate a more diverse range of words and expressions in their spoken English. The participants acknowledged that the engaging topics on Flipgrid motivated them to search for precise and impactful language, resulting in a broader and more nuanced vocabulary.

Relevance Of the Topics Motivates Speaking

The relevance of topics emerged as a critical factor influencing the participants' engagement with Flipgrid. Unlike generic language exercises, the

platform presented real-world topics that relate to the participants' lives and interests. The participants reported that the topics given for the videos are relevant and related to their culture and real-life experiences. This motivated them to speak freely as they could sing the Flipgrid Platform. The relevance of topics not only motivated students to participate actively in speaking exercises but also contributed to a deeper understanding of language use in real-world contexts. For instance, a participant explained that what he liked most about Flipgrid was that the topics were relevant to our lives. It made speaking about them more engaging and meaningful. It was not just about English; it was about expressing our thoughts on things happening around us."

What I liked most about Flipgrid was that the topics were relevant to our lives. It made speaking about them more engaging and meaningful. It wasn't just about English; it was about expressing our thoughts on things happening around us.

Another participant explained that the relevance of the topic to their real lives made the discussion easy and natural. This is what motivates him the most.

For me, the relevance of the topic to our real lives is what I liked most about Flipgrid. It made discussion easy and natural.

A participant also clarified discussing topics that matter to them is what made the use of Flipgrid enjoyable. For him, It was not just about English; it was about expressing their thoughts on things happening around them.

Discussing topics that matter to us made Flipgrid enjoyable. It was not just about English; it was about expressing our thoughts on things happening around us.

According to another participant, talking about real topics about things related to the participants' personal lives or culture is the most interesting part of the use of the Flipgrid. It motivated them to express themselves better.

Talking about real topics, talking about things that are related to myself or my culture is the most interesting part of the programme. It motivated me to express myself better.

The theme highlights the significance of meaningful content in language learning, as participants expressed heightened motivation in speaking when discussing topics of personal and societal relevance. It also suggests that the relevance of the topics played a crucial role in motivating students to diversify their vocabulary, emphasizing

the connection between meaningful content and language enrichment.

Challenges of Using Flipgrid in English Speaking Classroom

While the positive impact of Flipgrid on speaking skills was evident, the responses to the interviews also shed light on some challenges faced by the students during their interaction with the platform. The participants also reported that using Flipgrid in English speaking had some challenges which include technical hurdles, time constraints and internet issues. For instance, a participant explained that the only issue he had was the internet. Sometimes it took forever to upload my video, and he almost missed deadlines in some cases. He considered it frustrating because it was not under his control.

The only issue I had was the internet. Sometimes it took forever to upload my video, and I missed deadlines. It's frustrating because it's not something I can control.,

Another participant explained that not everyone has a good camera on their phone. He felt left out sometimes because his videos were not as clear as others. It is like, he was trying, but the tools were holding him back.

"Not everyone has a good camera on their phone. I felt left out sometimes because my videos weren't as clear as others. It's like, I'm trying, but the tools are holding me back."

Despite the benefits of the Flipgrid platform, a recurring challenge mentioned by students was technical issues. Some students faced difficulties in navigating the Flipgrid platform, especially during the initial phases of implementation. Connectivity issues and unfamiliarity with the user interface occasionally led to frustration among students. For instance, a participant explained that at first, the platform was a bit confusing. He had trouble figuring out how to use it, and there were times when his recording failed due to internet issues. It was a bit frustrating."

"At first, the platform was a bit confusing. I had trouble figuring out how to use it, and there were times when my recording failed due to internet issues. It was a bit frustrating."

Another challenge expressed by students was related to time constraints. Juggling academic commitments, extracurricular activities, and other responsibilities made it challenging for some students to consistently engage with Flipgrid. This was particularly true for those with tight schedules and demanding coursework. For instance, a participant explained that finding time for Flipgrid

was tough for him. He added that they had a lot on their plates with classes and assignments. Sometimes, he wished there was more flexibility time for them to record their videos."

Finding time for Flipgrid was tough. We have a lot on our plates with classes and assignments. Sometimes, I wished there was more flexibility in when we could record. (Participant 11)

While Flipgrid aimed to provide a private space for recording, some students still grappled with self-consciousness. The awareness that their recordings would be reviewed by peers or instructors led to heightened self-awareness and, in some cases, inhibited the natural expression of thoughts. A participant clarified that Even though it's not live, knowing that someone will watch his recording made him a bit self-conscious. He wanted to sound perfect, and that sometimes held him back.

Even though it's not live, knowing that someone will watch my recording made me a bit self-conscious. I wanted to sound perfect, and that sometimes held me back. (Participant 13)

Topic relevance variability is another challenge revealed by the interview responses. Although the relevance of Flipgrid topics was generally praised, a few students mentioned variability in how closely some topics aligned with their personal interests or academic focus. This led to varying levels of enthusiasm in contributing to discussions on certain subjects. For example, a participant explained that he found most topics interesting, but there were a few that he found less relevant to my studies. It made it a bit challenging to speak passionately about those.

While most topics were interesting, there were a few that I found less relevant to my studies. It made it a bit challenging to speak passionately about those.

Recognizing these challenges is crucial for educators and platform developers to enhance the overall effectiveness of technology integration in language learning. Addressing technical issues, providing flexible recording schedules, and ensuring a diverse range of topics that cater to students' varied interests could contribute to a more seamless and inclusive experience on the Flipgrid platform.

The findings of this study have several important implications for EFL teaching and learning. The use of Flipgrid significantly enhances student engagement and motivation, making speaking practice more enjoyable and dynamic. Through designing real-world speaking tasks aligned with students' interests and cultural contexts, teachers can sustain motivation and encourage active participation, which ultimately improves speaking proficiency. Additionally, Flipgrid enhances

collaborative learning by promoting peer interaction through video-based discussions, allowing students to develop critical thinking, listening, and interactive communication skills. This aligns with the social constructivist approach, emphasizing learning as a socially mediated process. The platform also encourages learner autonomy and reflection, as students can record, review, and refine their speaking performances at their own pace. This self-directed practice builds confidence, improves metacognitive skills, and reinforces lifelong learning habits. Furthermore, Flipgrid's asynchronous format helps to reduce speaking anxiety, offering a low-pressure environment where students can gradually build their confidence by starting with familiar topics before advancing to more complex tasks.

5. DISCUSSION

The findings of this study show that Iraqi EFL learners hold strongly positive perceptions of Flipgrid as an instructional tool for enhancing English learning especially speaking skills. Both quantitative and qualitative data demonstrate that Flipgrid supports speaking development by increasing practice opportunities to enhance motivation, collaboration, reducing speaking anxiety, and improving learners' confidence. The highest mean score among questionnaire items confirms that participants perceived Flipgrid as an effective platform for learning spoken English which highlights its value in EFL instruction.

The interview data further illuminate these findings by revealing several interrelated benefits of Flipgrid use. A key theme was anxiety reduction, as participants reported that the ability to record responses privately and re-record until satisfied helped alleviate fear of making mistakes. Unlike traditional face-to-face speaking tasks, Flipgrid's asynchronous format reduced time pressure and public embarrassment, allowing learners to focus more on fluency, pronunciation, and idea organization. This supportive environment encouraged risk-taking and increased willingness to speak in English an outcome particularly significant in contexts where speaking anxiety is prevalent among EFL learners.

Another prominent benefit was improved learner autonomy and self-reflection. Participants emphasized that repeated recording enabled them to monitor their own progress, refine pronunciation, and evaluate speech clarity before submission. Many students described the experience as similar to guided self-practice, reinforcing independent learning habits. In addition, Flipgrid's discussion

prompts promoted vocabulary development, as learners were motivated to explore appropriate lexical choices to express ideas clearly. The authenticity and relevance of the discussion topics further enhanced engagement and sustained participation, contributing to increased motivation toward speaking tasks.

Despite these positive outcomes, participants also identified several challenges associated with Flipgrid use. Internet connectivity problems were the most frequently reported limitation, particularly during video uploads, sometimes leading to frustration and delayed submissions. Technical constraints, such as limited access to high-quality recording devices and compatibility issues, also affected the quality of some students' recordings. Furthermore, although Flipgrid reduced speaking anxiety for most participants, a small number still experienced self-consciousness knowing their videos would be viewed by peers or instructors. These findings suggest that while Flipgrid is pedagogically effective, its successful implementation depends heavily on adequate technological infrastructure and learner support.

Within the Iraqi EFL context where traditional teacher-centered methods dominate and technological access is uneven the positive reception of Flipgrid reflects learners' readiness to engage with innovative, student-centered approaches. The observed reductions in anxiety and increased confidence are particularly noteworthy, given that speaking anxiety remains a major barrier to oral proficiency among Iraqi EFL learners. Flipgrid's capacity to provide a low-stakes, supportive environment thus represents a meaningful pedagogical shift toward communicative and learner-focused instruction. However, addressing infrastructural challenges remains essential for maximizing its effectiveness.

The findings of this study align closely with the theoretical frameworks underpinning the research. From a constructivist perspective (Vygotsky, 1978), learning occurs through social interaction and supported practice. Flipgrid facilitates collaborative learning through peer responses and feedback while offering scaffolding through repeated practice and instructor guidance. The reduction in speaking anxiety reflects the role of supportive environments within the Zone of Proximal Development, where learners gradually build competence and confidence through guided participation.

The results also support the Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989). Participants' positive perceptions of Flipgrid's usefulness such as improved fluency, confidence, and engagement and

its ease of use such as intuitive features and flexible participation contributed to high levels of acceptance. These factors increased learners' willingness to engage with the platform and their desire for its continued integration into speaking instruction, confirming TAM's central propositions.

Additionally, the findings correspond with the principles of the Task-Based Learning Approach (Ellis, 2003). Flipgrid's use of meaningful, discussion-based tasks encouraged learners to focus on communication rather than accuracy alone. Through repeated engagement with authentic speaking tasks, learners developed fluency, vocabulary, and confidence, consistent with TBL's emphasis on learning through purposeful language use.

The results of this study are consistent with previous research highlighting Flipgrid's effectiveness in EFL contexts. Improvements in fluency and confidence support findings by Diflippantonio-Pen (2020), while reductions in speaking anxiety align with studies by Tuyet and Khang (2020). The collaborative and motivational benefits reported echo Miskam and Saidalvi's (2019) findings, and vocabulary gains correspond with Mango's (2019) work on technology-supported language learning. Reported technical challenges also reflect concerns raised in earlier studies (Carville & Mitchell, 2020; Howard, 2013), reinforcing the need for institutional support.

6. CONCLUSION

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This study investigates the impact of FlipGrid on Iraqi EFL learners' motivation in learning English and to explore their perceptions of its use as a learning tool. The findings revealed a statistically significant improvement in learners' motivation after the FlipGrid-based intervention. The results indicated increased engagement, confidence, and willingness to participate in English learning activities. Furthermore, the learners expressed positive perceptions of FlipGrid, and viewed it as an interactive and motivating platform that supported communication and reduced anxiety, although some technical and connectivity challenges were reported. The study offers both theoretical and pedagogical contributions. It extends existing literature by providing context-specific evidence from Iraq and demonstrates the value of video-based discussion tools to enhance learner motivation in learning English. Practically, the findings suggest that FlipGrid can support learner-centered instruction and enhance motivation in EFL classrooms. However, the study has some limitations. The absence of a control group, the relatively small sample size drawn from a single university, and the short duration of the intervention may limit the generalizability of the findings. Future research should employ experimental designs with control groups, larger and more diverse samples, and longer intervention periods. Further studies may also examine the impact of FlipGrid on other language skills, particularly speaking proficiency, learner autonomy, and classroom interaction.

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